

Original Article

Prevalence of Self-Medication among Adults in Mirpur Azad Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract

The increasingly prevailing phenomenon of self-medication attracted the attention of researchers across societies. However, less is known about this phenomenon in the context of AJK. We attempted this research to shed light on this specific topic. Thus, we aimed to examine the determinants of self-medication prevailing among adults. We conducted this research in Sector-C of Mirpur, AJK. We used quantitative research design while employed cross-sectional research method. We collected data by using a questionnaire from a sample of 100 people by means of convenient sampling technique. The findings reveal a prevalent culture of self-medication among respondents, driven by factors such as convenience, cost considerations, and perceived self-efficacy. Despite being aware of the potential health risks, individuals continue to use medicine without physician's prescription. Self-medication appears to be gender-neutral, with people of all genders engaging in this practice. Additionally, self-medication is seen as cost-effective, as it allows individuals to avoid the expense of a physician's examination.

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Prevalence of Self-Medication among Adults in Mirpur Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 1(2), 1-10.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15292095>**Keywords:** Self-Medication, Education, Physician, Prevalence, Prescription

Introduction

The increasingly prevailing phenomenon of self-medication attracted the attention of researchers across societies. Studies on self-medication, Yeika et al. (2021) and Rathod et al. (2023) noted that people use medicine without consulting a doctor. Yeamans et al. (2024) also found that people perceived their self-care while using the medicine while Hasan et al. (2021) revealed that using medicine without advice of physician is dangerous and negatively impacts the health of users. This view is further supported by many studies conducted across the globe that people use self-medication for several reasons (Do et al., 2021; Karout et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2021; Meng et al., 2022). They unanimously argued that people use medicine at their own when they even feel a minimal level of illness. This practice has severe repercussions on the health of users. Miller (2023) and Schmits and Glowacz (2022) also added that due to the low cost and easy access to medicines, people use medicine without prescription of physician. By the same token, Steiner and Stovner (2023) maintained that adults use medicines without knowing the consequences in the long run. The findings of Arrais et al. (2016) are also like Jerez-Roig et al. (2014) who asserted that there is need to know about the prevalence of using medicines without prescription because it is harmful for health while bringing severe consequences. Ruiz (2010) emphasized that consuming the medicine substances in the absence of professional guidance is prevailing across societies.

This practice of consuming medicinal substances without professional guidance or a prescription, is a growing global concern among the general population (Kulkarni et al., 2018). This phenomenon is prevalent in developing countries while Pakistan and AJK have no exceptions (Arshad et al., 2024). Knowing prevalence, reasons, and consequences of self-medication is crucial for implementing effective interventions to promote responsible healthcare practices (Abbas et al., 2016).

This phenomenon is prevalent in most of the developing countries because people have access to all sorts of drugs (Jerez-Roig et al., 2014). They often consume drugs without a physician's prescription. Like Pakistan, people

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in AJK have access to all types of medicines (Aqeel et al., 2014). However, Seiter (2010) argued that the regulatory issues persist there because all the medicines are easily available from either pharmacies or medical stores on cheaper rates (Meng et al., 2022). Similarly, in AJK, people have access to all types of medicines and easily buy the drugs for use. To improve healthcare and reduce the use of self-medication, it is important to gather baseline data on self-medication, so that future interventions can be planned, and regulations can be implemented (Abdullah & Ullah, 2016; Saif et al., 2024).

Factors of Self-Medication

Research has been conducted on the continued use of medication at large scale across the globe (Meng et al., 2022; Jerez-Roig et al., 2014). These studies show that people diagnose illness at their own on the basis of symptoms they feel. Karout et al. (2021) maintained that people use drugs against illness continuously or intermittently while depending upon the causes of the illness. This practice, Lu et al. (2021) argued, has severe consequences on the health of users in the long run. Other researchers Baracaldo-Santamaría et al. (2022) and Yeika et al. (2021) told that people are using medicines without any prescribed criteria of physician. Similarly, Yeamans et al. (2024) highlighted that some people are using old prescription for long time while the condition of illness might need re-examination to know the extent of illness. They further stated that this situation is dangerous for the health of users as they might face some dire consequences to their health without using prescription of a physician. Besides, they may share medicines with others in their circles that further bring negative consequences to the health of others (Ruiz, 2010). It is noteworthy here that self-medication is one of the great health concerns the world over while World Health Organization (WHO) has already issued guidelines to curb the prevalence of such medicinal practices to avoid the self-medication (Perrot et al., 2019).

As stated earlier and reiterated here, using medicines without prescription of physician has many consequences. Primarily, it is wastage of time, money, and resources of the users. Although there is a timely relief, users become habitual in the long run and rely on wrong dosages. Thus, such practice may increasingly create resistance to the medicines against the pathogens (Jerez-Roig et al., 2014). Marak et al. (2016) argued that these practices are harmful to health. They also stated that whether such use of medicines has some benefits of relief, but risk factors are more likely associated with it (Abdullah & Ullah, 2022; Al-Worafi, 2020).

Researchers, Arrais et al. (2016) and Do et al. (2021) contend that there is a universal practice of using medicine by the people at their own, however it contributed to the human resistance of pathogens to these antibiotics (Abdullah & Kauser, 2022; Rather et al., 2017). Similarly, Hasan et al. (2021) found that awareness level of communities is low about the use of self-medication and such negative impacts may lead to severe consequences on the health of people (Chouhan & Prasad, 2016). While Jerez-Roig et al. (2014) revealed that the undue microbial use in the absence of prescription increases life threats to the users. Similarly, wrong treatment and diagnosis also poses increased resistance and even leads to morbidity in most cases. Bennadi (2013) further analysed that the use of allopathic medicines although help in relieving pain, but human body increase resistance against the drugs perpetuating to the skin issues and allergies (Shahzad et al., 2020).

Studies on self-medication indicate the benefits of using medicines by the users (Miller, 2023). For example, people themselves identify the symptoms of the illness. Similarly, they select the medicines and start treatment of the illness without consulting the physician. This helps them to save time, energy, and resources while saving huge prescription fees as well as avoid traveling. Likewise, it helps to reduce the pressure on the national medical services (Montastruc et al., 2016; Mustafa & Rohra, 2017). However, unguided medication use can result in significant individual risks of wrong diagnostics, severe health effects, resistance to antibiotics, dietary related issues and human resistance to the medicines (Ocan et al., 2015; Shoaib et al., 2024).

Several other factors influence the practice of self-medication including literacy levels, economic situation, availability and exposure to health care facilities, promoting medicines, information about diseases, and health insurance policy (Zeb et al., 2022). Access to information, availability of medications, promotion, experience, self-awareness and confidence, and leftover medications severely affected the health of users (Abdullah & Ullah, 2016; Siraj et al., 2022). Additionally, education levels, familial background, sociocultural environment, legislation gap, access to medicines are major contributing factors (WHO, 2008). Higher academic and professional levels are among the foremost factors influencing self-medication (Khalique et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2012). Prescribers and dispensers are especially vulnerable to self-medication due to their easy access to medications (Saha & Hossain, 2017).

Public awareness of using medicines with prescription has key importance in preventing improper usage of drugs among the people (Shahzad, et al., 2015; Camilleri, 2024). Studies have shown that many people avoid visiting healthcare facilities or professionals for medical advice (Abdullah, Habib, & Gillani, 2021; Rosenstock, 2005). This may be due to the easy access to health care and medicines by using media and social media tools that further contribute to the increased usage of medicines (Abdullah & Ullah, 2022; Chen & Wang, 2021).

In developing countries, it is common for individuals to resort directly to pharmacies instead of seeking medical consultation for care (Parulekar, 2016; Abdullah & Shoaib, 2021). Research also shows that in most of the developing countries, cost of healthcare and facilities, along with the high cost of physicians are the contributing factors that keep people away from visiting physicians and, thus, start self-medication (Ocan et al., 2015; Abbasi et al., 2016; Torres et al., 2019).

The rampant use of self-medication, particularly in the case of antibiotics, fosters the development of antibiotic resistance (Larsson & Flach, 2022; Manyi-Loh et al., 2018). To address this issue, experts suggest implementing healthcare plans like health insurance, restricting availability of such drugs in the market while strictly enforcing rules and regulation to the pharmacies to avoid drugs sale without prescription (Abdullah et al., 2015; Huemer et al., 2020).

Objective

The following objective guided our study.

1. To uncover the determinants of self-medication among the adults in Mirpur, AJK

Conceptualization

We conceptualized study and formulated the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis

There is association between self-medication and knowledge, medicine, gender, education and income.

Dependent Variable: Self-medication

Independent Variable: Knowledge, knowledge about medicine, gender, education and income.

Research Methodology

This study focused on the factors that influence the prevailing situation of self-medication among the adults in Mirpur AJK. The guiding objective of the study was to uncover the determinants of self-medication among the adults in Mirpur, AJK. For this purpose, we used positivistic epistemologies of quantitative research design as used by positivists to know the prevalence of self-medication among the people. Moreover, we employed cross-sectional research method to test the hypothesis of the study. The use of quantitative design was adopted owing to the availability of the data, time, and financial constraints while engaging the various variables at the same time in the analysis. This provides a greater understanding of the phenomenon under study. We conducted this research in one of the districts of AJK, i.e. Mirpur. We selected one of the sectors [Sector-C] of Mirpur City. We extracted a sample of 100 adults by means of Taro Yamane formula. This formula uses a simple and common mathematical model to determine the sample size from known population. We developed questionnaire and collected data from the 100 adults living in the surroundings. We collected data by using convenient sampling technique in line with the phenomenon under study because self-medication is a common issue of almost all people and most of the people are engaged and decide their illness at their own and select the medicine. We reviewed and refined the data and entered on the statistical packages for the social sciences (SPSS) and analyzed the data by employing the chi-square test. We tabulated the findings and interpreted in line with empirical research used in the research.

Key Findings

This part of the study highlights the main findings extracted from the analysis including frequency distribution and hypothesis testing.

These findings are tabulated and interpreted while results of hypothesis testing are included and explained with the help of empirical literature.

Frequency Distribution

Frequency distributions of each variable are tabulated and interpreted.

Table 1*Frequency Distribution of Demographic Variables.*

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent
18-23	47	35.3	35.3
24-29	41	30.8	30.8
30-35	19	14.3	14.3
40 and above	26	19.5	19.5
Total	133	100.0	100.0
Gender			
Male	87	65.4	65.4
Female	46	34.6	34.6
Total	133	100.0	100.0
Education			
Literate	124	93.2	93.2
Illiterate	9	6.8	6.8
Total	133	100.0	100.0
Occupation			
Employed	41	30.8	30.8
Unemployed	92	69.2	69.2
Total	133	100.0	100.0
Marital Status			
Married	61	45.9	45.9
Unmarried	72	54.1	54.1
Total	133	100.0	100.0
Income			
10000-20000	74	55.6	55.6
20001-30001	8	6.0	6.0
30002-40002	24	18.0	18.0
40003 & above	27	20.3	20.3
Total	133	100.0	100.0

Table 1 illustrates the frequency distribution table of age, gender, education, occupation, marital status, and income of the respondents. The demographic characteristics of the respondents are summarized in Table 1. The age distribution shows that the largest group of respondents was between 18-23 years, accounting for 35.3 percent of the total sample. This was followed by the 24-29 age group 30.8 percent, the 30-35 age group 14.3 percent, and those aged 40 and above 19.5 percent. In terms of gender, males constituted 65.4 percent of the sample, while females made up 34.6 percent. Regarding educational level, the majority of respondents were literate 93.2 percent, with only a small proportion being illiterate 6.8 percent. The occupational status of the respondents indicated that a significant majority were unemployed 69.2 percent, whereas 30.8 percent were employed. In terms of marital status, 54.1 percent of the respondents were unmarried, and 45.9 percent were married. Finally, the income distribution among the respondents revealed that more than half 55.6 percent had an income range of 10,000-20,000. A smaller percentage 6.0 percent had an income between 20,001-30,001, while 18.0 percent earned between 30,002-40,002, and 20.3 percent had an income of 40,003 and above. These demographic variables provide a comprehensive overview of the sample population, highlighting the diversity in age, gender, education, occupation, marital status, and income levels.

Hypothesis Testing

There is an association between self-medication and knowledge, gender, education, and income, and medicine.

Table 2*Chi-Square Distribution of Prevalence of Self-Medication.*

Independent Variables	Chi-square	df	P-value
Knowledge	37.635 ^a	1	.000
Gender	13.498 ^a	2	.001
Education	5.568 ^a	1	.018
Income	9.738 ^a	3	.021
Medicine	8.681 ^a	1	.003

Table 2 illustrates a strong association between self-medication and knowledge, indicating that individuals tend to engage in self-medication even when aware of its potential risks. Additionally, self-medication shows a significant relationship with gender, suggesting that both men and women are inclined to self-medicate. The data also reveals a significant correlation between self-medication and knowledge about proper medicine use. However, it is concerning that people continue to use self-medication despite being aware of its drawbacks. On the other hand, no significant relationship was found between self-medication and the respondents' education level or income.

Discussions

We discovered that individuals continue to use self-medication despite being aware of the potential risks associated with such practices. Similar findings were reported by Arshad et al. (2024), who, in alignment with Saif et al. (2024), analyzed self-medication and found that educated individuals are more likely to engage in it. Furthermore, Seiter (2010) also noted that self-medication is viewed as an easy alternative for people to treat illnesses without seeking professional consultation. Our study revealed that gender does not influence self-medication habits, as both men and women use medicines without a prescription. These findings are similar to the studies conducted by Ruiz (2010) and Roig et al. (2014). They unanimously stated that medicines are used by both men and women demonstrating gender neutrality. In addition, we found adults use medicine without any prescription despite knowing the negative effects of using medicine at their own. This means that adults using medicines find it an easy way to cure illness and avoid visiting physicians. Our findings are like those of Chouhan and Prasad (2016), they also maintained that adults start treatment themselves and do not intend to visit the physicians' clinic. Bennadi (2013) further argued, this phenomenon is widely practiced while adults despite having knowledge of serious effects of self-medication, use medicines to cure the illness. Here, we also found that the income and education level of adults does not affect the negative use of medicine. This trend is mainly prevailing among the general masses who might save their time and resources; however, it has severe consequences on health in the long run. The research of Mustafa and Rohra (2017) and Saha and Hossain (2017), also highlighted that adults use medicine either to save their financial resource or time to avoid visiting physician, but this trend carries dire consequences to their health leading towards the antibacterial resistance to the drugs.

Conclusion

The findings reveal a prevalent culture of self-medication among respondents, driven by factors such as convenience, cost considerations, and perceived self-efficacy. Despite being aware of the potential health risks, individuals continue to use medicine without a physician's prescription. Self-medication appears to be gender-neutral, with people of all genders engaging in this practice. Additionally, self-medication is seen as cost-effective, as it allows individuals to avoid the expense of a physician's examination. Although respondents demonstrate basic knowledge and caution when using medicine—such as checking expiry dates and reading labels—a notable number bypass professional medical advice, raising concerns about potential health risks. The responses indicate that while individuals have opinions about self-medication and report negative experiences, there is a clear need for better education and awareness regarding safe medication practices. Overall, the results emphasize the importance of promoting a balanced approach to health management, where self-reliance is complemented by professional medical guidance to prevent adverse outcomes and ensure effective treatment.

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